

ANALYTICAL MODELING AND SENSOR MONITORING
FOR OPTIMAL PROCESSING
OF POLYMERIC COMPOSITE MATERIAL SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Process simulation models and cure monitoring sensors are discussed for use in optimal processing of fiber-reinforced composites. Analytical models relate the specified temperature and pressure cure cycle to the thermal, chemical, and physical processes occurring in the composite during consolidation and cure. FDEMS (Frequency Dependent Electromagnetic Sensing) is described as an in situ sensor for monitoring the composite curing process and for verification of process simulation models. A model for resin transfer molding of textile composites is used to illustrate the predictive capabilities of a process simulation model. The model is used to calculate the resin infiltration time, fiber volume fraction, resin viscosity, and resin degree of cure. Results of the model are compared with in situ FDEMS measurements.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Modeling; Sensor; Manufacturing; Resin Transfer Molding.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fabrication of advanced composites is a complex, multi-step process which requires resin impregnation of the reinforcing fibers, orientation of the fibers in specified directions, and consolidation of the lay-up (or preform) by simultaneous application of

heat and pressure. The elevated temperature applied during cure provides the energy required to cause the desired physical and chemical changes in the matrix resin while the applied pressure compacts the structure. The magnitude and duration of the process temperatures and pressures coupled with the chemical state of the matrix critically influence the final physical and mechanical properties of the composite. A composite which is processed using an optimum cure cycle will result in a void-free structure which is uniformly cured to the desired fiber volume fraction and glass transition temperature.

The large number of material properties and processing parameters which must be specified and controlled during the manufacture of a composite laminate make trial-and-error procedures to determine the cure cycle impractical. Analytical models are clearly a far superior alternative for determining the optimum cure cycle. In situ sensors which can measure critical processing properties, such as viscosity and resin advancement, are essential for verifying the predictions of the analytical model, refining the model, and process monitoring under conditions which cannot be fully represented analytically. Both the analytical model and the sensing technology are required for a closed-loop intelligent production control system [1].

This paper will discuss the use of analytical models for simulating the curing and consolidation processes of fiber-reinforced composites and for selection of optimal processing cycles. Frequency dependent electromagnetic sensing (FDEMS) is described for in situ monitoring of the composite curing process and for verification of the model predictions. The paper will also discuss and demonstrate how process simulation models when combined with FDEMS measurements can be used to optimize the manufacture of polymeric composite material systems. Examples are taken from resin transfer molding (RTM) of textile composites.

2. CURE PROCESS MODEL

Analytical models have been developed which can be used to simulate the cure, resin flow and consolidation processes of composites fabricated by vacuum-bag, autoclave molding [2-5], filament winding [6-8], resin transfer molding [9-11], and pultrusion [12]. The process models usually consist of thermo-chemical and resin flow submodels. The thermo-chemical submodel is based on a heat transfer analysis coupled with cure kinetics and viscosity models which describe changes in resin viscosity and extent of cure due to chemical reaction during processing.

Modeling resin flow and consolidation during composite processing is commonly approached by assuming that the fiber network can be treated as a porous medium. Darcy's Law can then be used to describe resin flow in the composite. An excellent

review of the resin flow process during different composite fabrication methods is given by Dave' [13].

Additional models have been developed to describe the formation and growth of voids inside the composite microstructure during processing [2,14] and the residual stresses upon completion of processing [2,6]. The void and residual stress submodels can be combined with the thermo-chemical and resin flow submodels to form a comprehensive model of the composite fabrication process.

For a specified processing cycle, the models can be used to calculate the following parameters:

- a) The temperature distribution inside the composite;
- b) the temperature drop across the tooling, bleeders, and bagging material;
- c) the degree of cure of the resin as a function of position and time;
- d) the resin viscosity as a function of position and time;
- e) the resin flow, consolidation, and fiber/resin distribution as a function of time;
- f) the resin pressure distribution inside the composite;
- g) the void sizes, temperatures, and pressures inside the voids as functions of void location and time; and
- h) the residual stress distribution inside the composite after processing.

3. FREQUENCY DEPENDENT ELECTROMAGNETIC SENSING (FDEMS)

Frequency dependent electromagnetic sensing (FDEMS) has been shown to be a convenient automated instrumental technique for monitoring in situ the processing properties of thermoset resins continuously throughout the cure process. FDEMS is able to monitor the progress of cure including reaction onset, point of and magnitude of maximum flow, fluidity, solvent evolution, buildup in modulus, approach to Tg, reaction completion and degradation [5,15,16]. Measurements are made continuously throughout the entire fabrication cycle. Further, FDEMS can be used to evaluate and control resin properties prior to use, to provide a signature verifying the cure process during fabrication, and to provide in situ sensor feedback for intelligent, closed-loop control of fabrication.

The capacitance, C, and conductance, G, of the matrix resin are measured using the FDEMS sensor. The complex permittivity $\epsilon^* = \epsilon' - i\epsilon''$ is calculated from:

$$\epsilon' = \frac{C \text{ material}}{C_0} \text{ and } \epsilon'' = \frac{G \text{ material}}{C_0 2\pi f}$$

at each of 10 frequencies between 50 Hz and 1 MHz. This calculation is possible when

using a sensor whose geometry independent capacitance, C_0 , is invariant over all measurement conditions.

Both the real and the imaginary parts of ϵ^* have an ionic and dipolar component. The dipolar component arises from diffusion of bound charge or molecular dipole moments. The dipolar term is generally the major component of the dielectric signal at high frequencies and in highly viscous media. The ionic component often dominates ϵ^* at low frequencies, low viscosities and/or higher temperatures.

Simultaneous measurement of the frequency dependence of both ϵ' and ϵ'' or C and G in the Hz to MHz range is, in general, optimum for determining both the ionic mobility or conductivity, σ , and a mean dipolar relaxation time, τ . These two parameters are directly related on a molecular level to the rate of ionic translational diffusion and dipolar rotational mobility and thereby to changes in the molecular structure of the resin which reflect the reaction rate, changes in viscosity – modulus, and the degree of cure.

Figure 1 is a plot of the loss factor ϵ'' multiplied by the frequency ω measured by the sensor embedded inside a graphite–epoxy composite. Plots of ϵ'' multiplied by frequency ($\epsilon'' \cdot \omega$) are recommended because they conveniently display the frequencies and times where ϵ'' is dominated by ionic diffusion. That is, overlapping lines of ϵ'' multiplied by frequency indicate the frequencies and time periods when ϵ'' is dominated by ionic diffusion. At these frequencies, the ionic mobility can be tracked through the specific conductivity σ . The specific conductivity is calculated from the ionic component of ϵ'' (ϵ''_1) and the frequency (f).

The relationships of ϵ''_1 or σ to viscosity and degree of cure are determined through a series of isothermal resin characterization runs in the laboratory using FDEMS sensors, differential scanning calorimetry, and dynamic mechanical measurements of viscosity. These runs are used to construct a look–up table which relate the ionic mobility as tracked by σ for a particular temperature to the viscosity. A second independent look–up table was constructed relating σ for a given temperature to the degree of cure. These characterization matrices are used to determine the changing magnitude of the viscosity and the degree of cure at a particular position inside the composite from the FDEMS sensor output.

4. RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING

4.1 Infiltration/Cure Simulation Model Resin transfer molding (RTM) has been identified as a cost–effective manufacturing technique for fabricating damage tolerant composite structures with geometrically complex reinforcements. A model was

developed which can be used to simulate one-dimensional, through-the-thickness, nonisothermal infiltration of resin into a fabric preform and cure of the resin saturated preform. In the analysis, the fabric preform is modeled as a deformable porous medium and Darcy's Law is used to describe the resin flow process. Furthermore, the compaction characteristics (i.e., permeability-porosity relationship) of the preform are determined and incorporated into the model. Changes in viscosity and advancement of the resin are considered by incorporating cure kinetics and viscosity models into the analysis. Solution of the governing equations was obtained using the finite element technique. The infiltration/cure model is shown diagrammatically in Figure 2. Detailed descriptions of the model formulation and numerical procedures, and documentation of the experimental procedures followed to characterize the fabric preforms are given in reference 17.

For a specified compaction pressure and temperature cure cycle, the model can be used to predict the following parameters during infiltration and cure: a) initial resin mass; b) resin front position and preform infiltration time; c) preform temperature distribution; d) resin viscosity and degree of cure, and e) final part thickness and fiber volume fraction.

4.2 Composite Fabrication Textile composites were fabricated from Textile Technologies, Inc. eight harness satin fabric woven from Hercules IM7 graphite fibers (TTI 8HS/IM7) and Hexcel Hi-Tech multiaxial warp knit carbon fiber fabric. The fabric preforms were infiltrated with Hercules 3501-6 epoxy resin and cured using the mold assembly in Figure 3.

During layup, two Dek Dyne* FDEMS sensors and two type J thermocouples were placed inside the mold. A sensor and thermocouple were each placed on the bottom of the mold between the release film and the resin panel as shown in Figure 3. A second sensor and thermocouple were each placed on top of the graphite fiber preform. Thus the bottom sensor was able to make continuous measurements of the state of the resin at the bottom of the mold below the fabric. The top sensor was able to monitor the time it takes for the resin to infiltrate to the top of the fabric and the state of the infiltrated resin at the top of the mold.

4.3 Results For a specified processing cycle, the model can be used to predict the infiltration front position, infiltration time, and the fiber volume fraction. Figure 4 shows a comparison between the calculated and measured infiltration times for the Hexcel Hi-Tech preform. The experimental infiltration front position and time was obtained by measuring the displacement of the model plunger. Comparisons between

*Inquiries regarding the sensor and instrumentation should be directed to D. Kranbuehl.

the calculated and measured fiber volume fraction are shown in Figure 5. As can be seen from the figures, the measured values of infiltration time and fiber volume fraction agree well with the values calculated using the model.

The ability of the FDEMS sensor to monitor in situ infiltration and cure of the composite is demonstrated in Figures 6 and 7. Figure 6 is a plot of the loss factor ϵ'' multiplied by the frequency ω measured by the bottom sensor (sensor 1, Figure 3) during infiltration and cure of the TTI 8HS/IM7 fabric using the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle. Figure 7 is a similar plot for the sensor placed at the top of the TTI fabric preform (sensor 2, Figure 3) during RTM using the model generated rapid cure cycle. The beginning of resin flow at the bottom of the mold (Figure 6) and the time of resin infiltration to the top of the fabric preform (Figure 7) are readily seen as the time at which the magnitude of ϵ'' jumps several decades indicating resin wet-out of the sensor.

The resin viscosity and degree of cure are shown in Figures 8 and 9. Agreement between the model predicted and FDEMS sensor measured viscosity and degree of cure at the bottom of the preform (sensor 1, Figure 3) is good. These results demonstrate the ability of the FDEMS sensing technique to measure in situ the viscosity and degree of cure for model verification.

For this investigation, textile composites were fabricated using a model generated rapid cure cycle (see temperature cycle, Figure 7). Using the rapid cycle, complete infiltration of the preform is achieved without use of the manufacturer's recommended intermediate hold period and the total process cycle time was reduced by about 80 minutes.

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Analytical models have been developed which can be used to simulate the manufacture of continuous fiber-reinforced composites. The models can be used to determine the optimum cure cycle for a given application which results in a composite that is void free, and cured uniformly and completely in the shortest amount of time. Other important applications of the models include: a) performing sensitivity studies to identify the material and processing parameters that have the greatest effect on the curing process; b) identification of critical locations inside a composite part for placement of cure monitoring sensors; c) identification of the parameters that must be controlled and monitored during cure; and d) using the model as a cure simulator for the development of real-time, closed-loop computer software.

Frequency-dependent electromagnetic sensing (FDEMS) has been shown to be a convenient and reliable technique for in situ monitoring of the composite curing process.

FDEMS sensors placed inside the composite can directly monitor resin fluidity and advancement during fabrication. When properly calibrated, the output of the FDEMS sensors can be directly related to resin viscosity and degree of cure for comparison with the predictions of the simulation model.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was made possible through the support of the National Aeronautics and Space Administration—Langley Research Center grant no. NAG1—343 with Virginia Tech and grant no. NAG1—237 with the College of William and Mary.

7. REFERENCES

1. P. R. Ciriscioli, et al., SAMPE International Symposium, **35**, 1507 (1990).
2. A. C. Loos and G. S. Springer, J. Comp. Mat., **17**, 135 (1983).
3. R. Dave, J. L. Kardos, and M. P. Dudukovic, Polymer Composites, **8** (2), 123 (1987).
4. T. G. Gutowski, T. Morigaki, and Z. Cai, J. Comp. Mat., **21**, 172 (1987).
5. A. C. Loos and D. E. Kranbuehl, in H. P. Wang, ed., Intelligent Processing of Materials, MD—Vol. 21, ASME, New York, 1990, pp. 15—37.
6. E. P. Calius and G. S. Springer, International Journal of Solids and Structures, **26** (3), 271 (1990).
7. S. Y. Lee and G. S. Springer, J. Comp. Mat., **24**, 1270 (1990).
8. J. T. Tzeng and A. C. Loos, in M. Charmichi, et al., eds., Transport Phenomena in Materials Processing, HTD—Vol. 132, ASME, New York, 1990, pp. 131—139.
9. J. P. Coulter and S. I. Guceri, in T. G. Gutowski, ed., The Manufacturing Science of Composites, ASME, New York, 1988, pp. 79—86.
10. C. A. Fracchia, J. Castro, and C. L. Tucker, III, Proceedings of the American Society for Composites, 4th Technical Conference, Technomic Publishing Co., Inc., Lancaster, PA, 1989, pp. 157—166.
11. S. J. Claus and A. C. Loos, in ref. 10, pp. 147—156.
12. G. L. Batch and C. W. Macosko, in ref. 9, pp. 57—62.
13. R. Dave', J. Comp. Mat., **24**, 22 (1990).
14. J. L. Kardos, R. Dave', and M. P. Dudykovic, in ref. 9, pp. 41—48.
15. D. E. Kranbuehl in S. M. Lee, ed., Encyclopedia of Composites, VCH Publishers, Inc., New York, 1989, pp. 531—543.
16. D. E. Kranbuehl et al., ACS Division of Polymeric Materials: Science and Engineering, **56**, 163 (1987).
17. S. J. Claus and A. C. Loos, "A Cure Process Model for Resin Transfer Molding of Advanced Composites," Virginia Tech Center for Composite Materials and Structures, Report No. CCMS—89—07, April 1989.

Figure 1. $\text{Log}(\epsilon'' \cdot \omega)$ versus time.

Figure 2. RTM simulation model.

Figure 3. Schematic of the RTM lay-up and mold assembly.

Figure 4. Comparison between measured and model calculated infiltration times.

Figure 5. Fiber volume fraction as a function of compaction pressure.

Figure 6. Values of ϵ'' multiplied by frequency ($\epsilon'' \cdot \omega$) for the bottom sensor. Wet out of sensor occurs at 26 minutes.

Figure 7. Values of ϵ'' multiplied by frequency ($\epsilon'' \cdot \omega$) for the top sensor. Wet out of sensor occurs at 36 minutes.

Figure 8. Resin viscosity as a function of time at the bottom of the fabric preform. Comparison between FDEMS measured and model calculated values of resin viscosity.

Figure 9. Resin degree of cure as a function of time at the bottom of the fabric preform. Comparison between FDEMS measured and model calculated values of resin degree of cure.